

Evaluation of Capital Asset Pricing Model in Predicting Securities Returns at The Nairobi Securities Exchange (Listed Agricultural Companies)

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Abstract

The main purpose of this paper was to determine the impact of CAPMs systematic risk on securities returns and to determine the linearity of the risk and the returns. This study was guided by asset pricing theories in place which included the Arbitrage Pricing Model and Markowitz modern portfolio theory. This study targeted all agricultural companies listed and quoted under the NSE of which weekly prices for five years from January 2011 –December 2015 were used. This study used explanatory research design due to its quantitative nature while analyzing and interpreting data by use of statistical package for social science (SPSS) and excel spreadsheets. The findings show that the intercept is significantly not different from zero, for years 2011, 2012, 2013 and 2014 at 5% level of significance implying that the excess of actual returns are explained by the systematic risk while the intercept for year five is significant implying that the securities excess actual returns are not fully explained by the systematic risk. Thus, the five year period CAPM is consequently able to fairly capture the pattern of actual excess returns in the Kenya NSE. The study found out that, higher betas yields to higher return which is consistent with the CAPM model. Thus, the five year period CAPM is consequently able to capture the pattern of returns and risk in the Kenyan perspective despite being non-linear. The significance of this study is that shareholders, corporate managers, financial analysts and other stakeholders will enhance their investment risk management.

Keywords: CAPM model, systematic risk, securities returns, intercept, beta coefficient

Introduction

Capital asset pricing model (CAPM) is an important theory in finance. It is widely used in different areas within the finance discipline including but not limited to funds management, real estate financing, banking, mergers and acquisitions, evaluation of warrants and convertible securities and also an appraisal of investments to determine their viability after establishing the cost of finance. It is a tool that uses the systematic risk or the beta coefficient to determine or predict returns expected in an investment and therefore exploring their relationship (Martin & Maria, 2014)

CAPM was first introduced by Sharpe (1963), supported by Lintner (1965) and many more recent researchers including Pamane and Anani (2014), Zhi and Ravi (2012), Mehnaz and Nafiz (2017) Wakyiku 2010 among others. Their desire was to find a tool that could be used in finance to show the relationship between risks that could not be reduced even after diversification, with the returns earned thereto. This was powered by the fact that a risk that could be reduced by holding more securities is not actually risked because ways and means of averting it could be devised as quickly as possible to normalize operations. This was after Markowitz (1952) showing that investors prefer investments that yield good returns but have lower risk and are liquid. Markowitz concentrated on the unsystematic risk while Sharpe delved into the systematic risk.

The argument surrounding the systematic risk or the beta coefficient is to introduce the risk that an investor cannot minimize by holding more securities or assets. This risk compensates the investor since the effect is felt across all companies. These risks include political risk, weather conditions, terrorism (like acts of Al-Shabaab, ISIS and the like), and natural calamities like earthquakes and so on and so forth. This risk is therefore determined by first looking at the co-movement of the market returns and those of the security or portfolio in question and also the variance of the market. This beta coefficient determines the sensitivity of a securities returns as a result of market changes (Fama, 2004).

Betas greater than one indicates that the securities return are more sensitive to market changes hence referred to as aggressive. Betas less than one indicates that the assets returns are less sensitive to market changes and hence known as defensive betas. Those assets that have betas that are equal to one are considered to have the same changes as those of the market while those that have betas equal to zero are considered to be risk-free assets like the treasury bills.

The CAPM model in any market should be a good predictor of an investor's returns which in an actual sense should be the one that brings efficiency in valuation. This efficiency is mathematically established when the intercept constant is significantly not different from zero given the respective margin of error determined from the stated confidence interval chosen. In trying to find a tool that could be accurately or near accurately be used to predict returns of securities in a stock exchange, recent researchers have tried to modify the original CAPM model to litigate on its limitations. The Fama –Macbeth (2003) 3-factor model and the Fama-French (2005) 5-factor model offer appropriate examples. Zhou and Li (2016) further improved the Fama-French (2015) 5-factor model. They introduced the non-normal error term and disturbances that were time variant. All these efforts were aimed at providing a model that can be wholly reliable.

Modern theories of finance are based on the rationality of markets. This model is the CAPM. The consequences of not accepting the rationality of markets as put forward by the CAPM are very significant. In acknowledgment of the fact that markets are characteristically rational, the CAPM has developed finance to be an important subject in economic studies. Firms have grown to acknowledge the CAPM for the approximation of the cost of capital for the valuation of investments in the firm and setting selling prices in utility regulation (Akwimbi, 2003). Similarly, it has been used to set bonuses for executive managers linked to value addition. The idea of market prudence has tentatively been used to justify an idea of arms-length market regulation on the ground that the market is knowledgeable and that it can correct it. An empirical review of the CAPM is, however, contradicting the academic analysis notion of rationality.

Every investor would like to form optimum investment decisions that can secure an appropriate degree of returns that are in line with the amount of risk taken for them. Regrettably, it is not easy to obtain the profile data, and in the case where it is obtained, the cost could be so big that it results in a decrease in the level of expected returns or negative returns. Some reviews on this issue have been conducted on the NSE in Kenya regarding the relationship between the risk and return. In this case, the Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT) as a linear model properly explains the NSE expected return of the stocks (Akwimbi, 2003).

It is theoretically plausible to expect the effect of risk on the returns of a given portfolio or a stand-alone investment although sector by sector. Risk needs to be analyzed to find out the consistency or non-consistency with other scholars (Munene, 2014). This has in effect informed the current study to fill up the gap identified.

Apuoyo (2010) and Nyaata (2009) conducted similar studies, and in their findings, they, however, found a small difference between APT and CAPM prediction methodologies. Gichana (2009), in his comparison of linear and non-linear models applicability on the securities exchange, concluded that non-linear models are better predictors of return with risk. past scholars have found out that these shifts have influenced the computations of risk return. This gap is what informed the current study. The research niche in Kenya as alluded by the studies cited above and other studies abroad reviewed has been lack of individual sector risk-return relationships which need to be tested using CAPM. In most of the cases, the non-linear APT models have been applied to make conclusions and recommendations on the listed companies of either the whole economy or particularly given segments of the NSE like the MIMS and the AIMS. This study has to be compelled to address the gap by establishing whether or not there exist risk-return patterns relationship for listed companies at the NSE specifically for the agricultural sector by the utilization of linear model of the CAPM theory. The matter of sector by sector portfolio valuation, thus ends up in the subsequent analysis question(s); will CAPM give correct results once used for study involving evaluation of securities of a given

sector in associate economy at the securities market?, and will its effect be essential for the financiers while assessing the securities and the risk. Nairobi securities exchange (NSE) gives a good platform to study the applicability and validity of the CAPM. This is because it is where all securities of all sectors of the Kenyan economy are traded and hence it gives a representative view of Kenya's economy of which the findings can be used to generalize on the performance of the given sector. Prices are also determined by the market forces of demand and supply which are in line with the CAPMs assumption. Thus, the study hypothesized that:

H₀₁: CAPM does not predict securities returns of agricultural companies in the NSE

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on Arbitrage Pricing Theory. In search of a substitute security appraisal model to the CAPM that was realistically instinctive, needed only a small group of assumptions and allowed for many dimensions of investment risk, the APT was developed by Ross in 1976. This theory has been examined in many markets to determine if it is contrary to the CAPM. This theory defines the price when the mispriced asset is not priced properly with regard to the market. While the CAPM methodology requires the expected rate of return of the market, APT utilizes the individual assets' forecasted rate of return as well as the premium risk of different macroeconomic variables. Those in support of APT utilize it to benefit by leveraging on the securities that have been mispriced because it offers the opportunity for arbitrage. Thus, a mispriced security can have a different worth from the hypothetical worth put forward by the model. Ross (1976) also notes that by going short on expensive security whereas going long in the portfolio at the same time, the APT computations are pegged on the supported of APT who are in a better place to earn a profit that is risk-free. Jordan (2017) in his article on macroeconomic forces and arbitrage pricing theory, tried to find out the effect of major macroeconomic variables on stock returns. The variables included a risk premium, industrial production, expected inflation, unexpected inflation and the term structure. Not all variables tested affected the domestic stock returns from the sample of the six countries in question. Under the arbitrage pricing model, each variable has its own beta coefficient(Oyetayo & Adeyeye, 2017). The model did not exhibit a clear linear association between the beta coefficient and the expected returns since out of the five variables; only two were linear while the other three were non-linear (French, 2017).

APT is based on the notion of the security worth being determined by different elements and may be either macroeconomic or firm based. The APT could be a substitute for the CAPM since each model asserts a linear connection between securities expected returns and their variance with alternative random elements (Ross, 1976). The difference between CAPM and APT lies in the fact that CAPM integrates a single non-company issue and one beta while APT differentiates out non-firm elements into several where necessary. This means that each of these elements requires a different beta. The beta of each issue is the sensitivity of the asset worth to that element. The outcome of the APT equation (R_i), is the actual rate of return on a security i , all through a given period. The dependent variables include a constant factor, $E(R_i)$. This is the expected rate of return for security i given all the opportunity elements have zero changes. The response in an asset i 's returned to movements (back) in a common risk issue (k) and (δk) that could be a group of common elements or indices with zero mean that affects the returns on all assets. The equation has a disturbance δ_i that is assumed to be zero because it is totally diversified in massive portfolios. APT doesn't believe in the measurement of the achievement of the market; rather it directly communicates the worth of the security to the basic elements determining it. The matter with this can be that the speculation essentially provides no indication of what these elements are so that they have to be compelled to be through empirical observation determined. The possibly sizable amount of things suggests that a lot of betas to be calculated and there's additionally no guarantee that all the relevant factors are known (Sharpe, 1992). As a result, the APT is tough to place into following paper on rigorous fashion.

Effect of the magnitude of betas on securities returns in the agricultural sector

CAPM has been subjected to numerous observational tests in view of various ramifications of the connection between expected return and beta coefficient as propounded by the model. To start with, expected returns for all assets are directly identified with their betas, and no other variable has minor elucidatory control. Next, the assets premium is certain, implying that the expected market return surpasses the expected return for assets whose profits are uncorrelated with the market return. Last, assets uncorrelated with the market have anticipated that profits equivalent would be the hazard free loan fee, and the benefits premium is the normal market return less the risk-free rate (Fama and French, 2004) which is equivalent to zero.

Some early experimental reviews (Black, Jensen and Sholes, 1972; Fama & MacBeth, 1973; Sharpe & Cooper, 1972; Litzenberger and Ramaswamy, 1979; Gibbons, 1982; Chan & Lakonishok, 1993) on the CAPM are sensibly strong of the essential central of the model. Black, Jensen & Sholes ;1972) found over the period 1931-1965 that the higher beta risk and higher return go hand in hand. Fama & MacBeth (1973) likewise found over the period 1935-1968 that beta and returns were emphatically related for the whole period and for eight of nine sub-periods and in addition the relationship to be direct, and unsystematic risk did not influence returns. Chan & Lakonishok (1993) called attention to over the period 1926-1991 that betas are a valuable manual for risk in extraordinary economic situations, with the most hazardous firms performing far more awful than the market in general, in the ten most noticeably bad months for the market between those years. It has been demonstrated that risk is identified with vulnerability, which is basically is related to the expected results from that security. Besides, the aggregate risk of putting resources into a security is made out of two particular dangers which are, systematic risk and unsystematic risk.

CAPM clarifies one of them, especially, the danger of being in the market (Malkiel & Xu, 2006). Regardless of how we enhance our speculations, it's difficult to dispose of all the hazards. Speculators merit a rate of return that repays them for going out on a risk. The CAPM causes us to ascertain venture risk and what degree of profitability we ought to anticipate. The response variable or result of the CAPM condition, R_j is the return on the j th portfolio. The autonomous factors comprise of R_f which is the risk-free rate, β_j which is the beta of the j th portfolio and R_m which is the return of the market portfolio return. The contrast between the market portfolio return and the risk-free rate is then increased by the beta. This can be communicated as;

$$E(R_j) = R_f + (R_m - R_f) \beta_j \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (i)}$$

Where;

$E(R_j)$ = Expected return of security j ,

R_f = Risk-free rate,

β_j = Beta of the security j ,

$E(R_m)$ = Expected return on the market,

$E(R_m) - R_f$ = Market premium.

The CAPM formula can be re-written as follows ,

$$A(R_j) - R_f = \alpha_j + (R_m - R_f) \beta_j \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (ii)}$$

Where $A(R_j)$ = actual returns of security j .

α_j = alpha which is the intercept.

The model conjointly contends that there's a positive direct connection between the expected rate of profit for a security and its beta coefficient value, which implies that the expected return higher than the riskless rate is straightly related to the non-diversifiable risk as measured by the asset's beta. Black, Johannes Vilhelm Jensen & Scholes, 1972), Fama & Macbeth (1973) , demonstrated that there's a positive connection between the beta coefficient and the expected return, while portfolios with higher beta value have a superior yield, which is in concurrence with the model's presumptions.

While assessing CAPM on the rising markets of the central and South Eastern Europe (Josipa & Aljinović, 2013) broke down month to month information of stock returns for nine nations for a time of January 2006

to December 2010 by utilization of excel spreadsheets of which the consequences of expected profits for stock and their betas were relapsed by utilization of the SPSS package. The consequences of this examination are that disregarding everything, nine nations' stocks had been tried and there was the conclusion that the model was not an agent, however additionally not factually critical in all nations, which makes the likelihood of applying the CAPM in these business sectors extremely dicey. Since the coefficient of direct connection measures the connection amongst beta and expected returns, the test outcomes demonstrated that for all nations aside from the Czech Republic and Bosnia and Herzegovina a frail relationship was set up. Be that as it may, these outcomes ought to be brought away with a grain of salt since the example of offers for these two nations was not the same concerning different markets.

In South Africa capital asset pricing model has been reviewed with the intention of computing the cost of capital that investment practitioners use in evaluating their portfolios, Soon Noel (2011). The study in South Africa sought to find out if there exist a niche between CAPM in academia and the one being used in practice.

CAPM has conjointly been tested in Nigerian securities market where a hundred and ten listed corporations were evaluated. The outcomes commonly negate the CAPM's forecasts that higher risk (beta) is identified with a superior level of profits which the catch should be up to zero once evaluating the security market line (SML). The claim by the CAPM that the SML incline should rise to the surplus profits for the market portfolio is moreover not bolstered by this review. This essentially nullifies the expectation of the CAPM in Nigerian capital market (Oke, 2013). Nwude, (2013) looked to see if CAPM is a decent indicator of expected returns in the Nigerian oil market and the researcher discovered that there was 100% failure of CAPM as a device of assessing stock returns. In the Egyptian market, an analysis of the CAPM was done between 2001 and 2002. The study was for thirty-two corporations listed within the Egyptian market whereby the information was collected from Al Ahram newspaper of Egypt. (Omran, 2007), opines that there's verification reaffirming the adequacy of applying portfolio hypothesis and CAPM in the Egyptian market. The outcomes showed that the systematic risk, as measured by beta and inclination for asymmetry hopes to assume a noteworthy part of the profits progression inside the Egyptian securities market.

In Kenya CAPM as an asset pricing model has been tested in the Nairobi securities exchange where the independent variables propounded by the three asset-pricing models that designate the expected returns on stocks have been examined. These variables include excess market return, size effect, book-to-market equity and also the momentum effect. The analysis was done for the activities listed stocks on the NSE under the Main Investment Market Segment (MIMS), within the period January 2009 to December 2013. For CAPM to be valid, the intercept coefficient should not be significantly different from zero. However, According to (Riro & Wambugu, 2015), it can be observed that the intercept coefficients for portfolios formed were all significantly different from zero based on their t-values which are larger than the critical t-value. Therefore, the test of CAPM indicates that when tested from a portfolio perspective, the evidence in support of it in the NSE is weak. Instability can be reduced by having an appropriate expansion of securities, Sharpe contended that a portfolio's expected profit depends exclusively for its beta, that is, its relationship to the general market.

CAPM helps with evaluating portfolio beta coefficient and the expected return related with that risk element. Return is the quantitative measure of how a venture performs. It speaks to the rate increment in the financial specialist's riches coming about because of what the speculation produces. On account of stocks, the arrival is the rate change in cost in addition to the profit yield (Tellis & Johnson, 2007). It is basic to contend that the normal profit for an advantage ought to be emphatically identified with its risk. A financial specialist will consent to hold an advantage considered risky given that its normal return repays for that risk. Beta measures the methodical risk segment of security with respect to that of the market portfolio. The security showcase line graphically represents the CAPM equation and demonstrates that the connection amongst risk and expected return is a straight line with a positive incline (Kamau, 2002). It gives financial investors a

device for judging whether securities are underestimated or exaggerated given their level of deliberate (beta) risk. For the most part, it is acknowledged that legitimacy of a hypothesis relies on upon the observational exactness of its expectations instead of on the authenticity of its presumptions (Da, 2009). This hypothesis has been liable to different reactions key among them being that the single market beta should be supplemented with extra measurements of risk.(Josipa & Aljinović , 2013) needed to check CAPM on the business sectors of nine nations of focal and south-eastern Europe for a period starting January 2006 to December 2010 that included; European country, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Bulgaria, Republic of Croatia and Turkey, Serbia and Bosnia Herzegovina. They set up that, CAPM isn't satisfactory for evaluating the capital assets on learned Central and South European rising markets.

Riro and Wambugu (2015) started the review to decide if CAPM, Fama, and French (1993), three issue model and Carharts four issue model may clarify the profits listed the NSE, from a portfolio viewpoint. They used returns from forty-eight firms that traded in the MIMS section of the NSE for the duration of January 2009 to Dec 2009. They observed that despite the fact that the CAPM has been extremely regarded for several years, once tested at the NSE from a portfolios perspective; the proof in support of it is weak. The study observed that important alternative issue exists that wasn't captured by CAPM, implying thus that beta isn't associate an adequate measure of risk. The proof of CAPM from the portfolios perspective is weak, (Riro &Wambugu, 2015). The scholars came to a conclusion that the weakness of the CAPM could also be as a result of alternative factors that weren't thought-about in their study.

Various studies have been undertaken both domestically and internationally to explore the connection of evaluation of securities of quoted companies. (Kamau, 2002) surveys the association of organizations cited on the Main Investment Market phase (MIMS) and furthermore the Alternative Investment Market phase (AIMS). The review utilized ad hoc market information from the NSE for the term of January 1996 and December 2000. Individual companies Sharpe Ratios for the whole duration were computed and analyzed. Variations between Sharpe Ratios of companies listed below the MIMS and those of companies listed below AIMS were analyzed based on Wilcoxon Rank sum test usually applied wherever two samples are analyzed. The examination watched that there was no essential qualification regarding the rate of return and risk between those organizations recorded underneath the MIMS and AIMS.(Gitari, 1990) discovered that organizations exchanging the Kenya's NSE demonstrate a positive connection amongst hazard and returns. The association was yet not imperative, in this way suggesting financial specialists could wind up being paid pretty much to take up high risks.

Munywoki (1998) in his review led learns at the NSE to appraise systematic risk, of which the researcher assessed it to be at 3.5%, and the market comes back to be 14.8%. The review moreover ascertained the NSE beta to be 0.9002 ascribing the qualification between his measurable beta and furthermore the beta of 1.0 to sampling.

Ombajo (2006) conducted a review to see the degree that NSE market division influenced the offer expenses and costs of listed firms, liquidity and speculator acknowledgment. The review system spearheaded by (Fama *et al.* 1969) was utilized as a part of directing the review. The study focused on the MIMS and also the AIMS. (Akwinbi, 2003) studied the NSE by applying APT for predicting stocks rate of returns and established that APT model had a lot of success in explaining the expected return on the NSE and declared that the APT model holds true for new markets.

Material and Methods

The explanatory research design was used in this review. In this study, the target population comprised all listed companies operating in Kenya securities exchange which is from the agricultural sector. The study expects to analyze the stock returns of all the seven listed companies in the agricultural sector in the Nairobi Securities Exchange. This study used average monthly stocks returns from the listed companies through document analysis in the NSE for the period of 5 years running from 1st January 2011-31st December 2015 was adopted, and the data was obtained from the NSE offices in the form of daily costs or prices hence

classified as longitudinal data. The data used was therefore purely secondary data sourced from NSE. This study used the average monthly prices for a stock to represent monthly data and NSE 20 share index as the representative of the market index. The index was an estimated weighted normal index containing 20 most exchanged securities of the market. The average 91 days Treasury bill for one year was utilized as an intermediary for the risk-free rate. Every single stock return utilized with the end goal of this review was not to be reduced for dividends.

Model specification

To test the CAPM for the firms in the agricultural sector quoted and recorded at the Nairobi securities trade, this review arranged raw ad-hoc data for a time of 5 years from January 2011 to December 2015 where average month to month prices was figured utilizing Microsoft Excel and SPSS. The average return for the NSE 20 share index was utilized as an intermediary for the market return while the 91-day treasury bill rate was utilized as an intermediary of the risk-free rate of return. Individual stock return and market return was calculated in accordance with the following formula proposed by Brealey *et al.* (2005):-

$$R_t = \frac{(P_t - P_{t-1})}{P_{t-1}} \times 100$$

P_{t-1}

Where:

R_t =Monthly stock return

P_t =Average price of a share in the current month.

P_{t-1} =Average price of a share in the previous month.

The next step was to determine the beta coefficient for every stock of each company using the monthly returns of the stock and those of the market. The unstandardized beta coefficient is arrived at by using the following formula:

$$\text{Beta}(\beta) = \frac{\text{Cov}_{(in)}}{\delta_m^2}$$

where :

$\text{Cov}_{(in)}$ covariance of the stock and market while

δ_m^2 is a variance of the market.

In conjunction with the above formula, ordinary least squares (OLS) was used to determine the standardized beta coefficient. Upon determination of the beta coefficient, the data was regressed using the CAPM formula to determine the expected returns. The excess expected returns were compared with the excess market returns so as to determine the effectiveness of the CAPM model by determining the value of the intercept using the following formula which was given earlier (Equation ii) above as $A(R_j) - R_f = \alpha_i + (R_m - R_f) \beta_j$. Finally, the T-statistic at 95% confidence interval was established to determine whether the intercept is significant or not so as to facilitate interpretation. R-square was also determined to find out the extent to which systematic risk explains the occurrences of the excess returns on an asset. This is with the help of excel spreadsheets and statistical program for social science (SPSS).

Findings and Discussion

This part explains mean of the returns giving the maximum and the minimum values in addition to standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis. The data in Table 4.1 shows the descriptive statistics in relation to the explanatory factors, RF and RM and the response factor AR between the years 2011 to 2015. This examination is in terms of the mean as well as the tests of normality of the data in this period. The findings shown in Table 1 indicate that in the year 2011, the mean RF was 12.8, then dropped to 8.91 in 2012 before slightly increasing to 8.93 in 2013 after which a big leap was experienced in 2014 to 10.8 and finally a big drop to 8.65. The maximum and minimum values each year were separately the same which gave a separate equal mean each year of study. This led to a zero standard deviation for each year of study. This is the

reason as to why it is referred to as the risk-free rate and the 91-day treasury bill referred to as a risk-free asset. (Muhammad et al.; 2012) gave a similar opinion in his study of the CAPM.

Table 1 further shows the changes experienced in the market return which in 2011 the mean RM was -0.6358 [min -2.01 max 0.95]. There was an increase of the mean RM in 2012 to 0.1525 which further increased to 0.5592 in 2013 before slightly reducing in 2014 and finally a big decrease in the year 2015. As a result of the fluctuations, there were recorded different magnitudes of standard deviations which initially arise due to different values of the minimum and maximum values as shown in the table. The deviation of 2011 was recorded as 0.95621 while that of 2012 was 0.40993. The one for 2013 was valued at 1.02055 while that of 2014 was 0.39653 and finally for 2015 was recorded as 1.00108. As the value decrease, it indicates that the deviations from the mean for that particular year were less as compared to the value when it increases which signifies that there are huge deviations of the market returns from the mean. The fluctuations experienced through the period of study indicates the changes in risks for each end every year.

The actual returns are also indicated in table 1 which shows various fluctuations of increase in the decrease. The mean returns in 2011 were 0.065 which improved to 0.135 in 2012 and further increases in 2013 to 0.3933 before again improving to 0.5442 in 2014 and finally a further increase to 0.885 in 2015. The standard deviations vary from 1.32843 to 0.8664 to 0.86646 to 1.72152 and finally to 1.89293 for years 2011,2012,2013,2014 and 2015 respectively. The values measure the rate of dispersion from the mean value.

The results in Table 1 indicate how the data for actual and market returns have been distributed. This is shown the values of skewness which are all positive except actual returns of 2013 which is negative. A positive value shows that the data are skewed to the right while the negative value indicates that the data is skewed to the left. The fluctuations of risk-free and the securities returns indicate the sensitivity caused by market changes as contained in the systematic risk measured by the beta coefficient. The data is normal for all the years for RM except for 2014 indicating non-normality.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for 2011-2015

		Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
2011	ar	-2.01	2.91	0.065	1.32843	0.781	0.931
	rm	-2.01	0.95	-0.6358	0.95621	0.421	-0.723
	rf	12.8	12.8	12.8	0	.	.
2012	ar	-1.16	1.57	0.135	0.8664	0.482	-0.671
	rm	-0.55	0.81	0.1525	0.40993	0.123	-0.496
	rf	8.92	8.92	8.9194	0	.	.
2013	ar	-1.42	1.72	0.3933	0.86446	-0.716	0.532
	rm	-1.22	2.65	0.5592	1.02055	0.345	0.691
	rf	8.93	8.93	8.9307	0	.	.
2014	ar	-2.73	3.87	0.5442	1.72152	0.177	0.71
	rm	-0.3	1.12	0.1417	0.39653	1.358	2.536
	rf	10.83	10.83	10.8262	0	.	.
2015	ar	-1.64	3.78	0.885	1.89293	0.345	-1.147
	rm	-1.83	1.31	-0.5154	1.00108	0.435	-1.014
	rf	8.65	8.65	8.6501	0	.	.

AR = actual returns, RF = risk free, RM = market portfolio return

Beta Coefficients

The OLS regressions of the 5 value-weighted portfolios are summarized in Table 2. Tests which were carried out intended to assess if the market portfolio of β explains the different actual returns by concentrating on the intercept estimates the intercept estimate here is given by the difference between the

actual returns and the CAPM returns. First, the estimation of betas and for each period equivalent average beta value was obtained.

Table 2: Weighted Portfolios Statistics For The Five Periods

	R	Constant	Significance	Estimated	Significance
	squared	(α_i)	Level	Beta (B)	Level
2011	0.366	0.599	0.155	0.840	0.037
2012	0.024	0.085	0.766	0.329	0.630
2013	0.525	0.127	0.535	0.725	0.008
2014	0.421	-0.016	0.972	1.180	0.022
2015	0.603	1.642	0.002	1.469	0.003

Table 2 displays the beta coefficient values for each year of estimation. After applying descriptive statistics to the beta approximations in Table 4.12, the lowest value of beta was 0.329, and the higher value was 1.469. Table 2, shows that one (1) of the five (5) intercepts significantly different from zero (0) which is the one for the year 2015. These findings mean that the portfolios of the market are not fully accounted for by the elements in the full period CAPM. The full period CAPM is therefore not able to completely capture the change of portfolio returns. The R Squared range between 2.4% and 60.3% for the 5 portfolios. However, R-square below 20% can be perceived as having low explanatory power in explaining actual excess returns from the risk-free rate of return.

For evaluating the CAPM, t-tests are used to analyze if the average risk premium is positive and to see if the intercept equals zero. The linear risk-return connection is assessed based on a two-sided t-test to determine whether the actual return distribution is affected by the systematic risk only. These findings from the five year period confirm those of Black, Jensen, and Scholes (1972), Fama and Macbeth (1973) who found out that there is a positive linear relationship between beta and the expected return, while portfolios with higher beta have a better yield. This is also in agreement with the assumption of the model. In addition, Gitari (1990) established that companies trading in the Kenya's NSE show a positive relationship between risk and returns. Nonetheless, Josipa and Aljinović (2013) concluded that the regression model is not illustrative and characteristic and also not statistically significant in all countries. This makes the possibility of applying the CAPM model in these markets significantly uncertain. As a result, they concluded that CAPM is not adequate for examining the capital assets on the given Central and South European emerging markets.

The ordinary least squares of the 5 portfolios are presented in Table 3. The tests were carried out to establish whether the market portfolios of β explain the different actual returns by focusing on the intercept estimate of the regression model. The findings in Table 4.13 present the regression model intercept and determines whether it is equal to zero or not.

Table 3: Beta coefficient in 2011-2015

Random-effects GLS regression		Number of obs = 35				
Group variable: firm		Number of groups = 7				
R-sq: within = 0.0000		Obs per group: min = 5				
between = 0.0000		avg = 5				
overall = 0.4951		max = 5				
		Wald chi2(1) = 32.37				
corr(u_i, X) = 0 (assumed)		Prob > chi2 = 0.000				
ar	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P>z	[95% Interval]	Conf.
market	4.239846	0.7452622	5.69	0.000	2.779159 5.700533	
_cons	1.816142	0.3420821	5.31	0.000	1.145673 2.48661	
rho	0.00000					

The findings in the regression model summarized in Table 3 show that the intercept is equal to zero, ($\beta_0 = 1.816$, p -value = 0.000) at 5% level. This means that the portfolio of the market in the five years from 2011-2015 is fully accounted for by the elements contained in the 5 year period CAPM. Thus, the 5 year period CAPM is, as a result, able to fully explain the outline of portfolio returns of agricultural companies in Kenya. This is supported by the t-statistic of 1.896 which is within the range of ± 1.96 which in essence means that the null hypothesis that the intercept is equal to zero is failed to be rejected. The R square of 49.51% for the five portfolios indicates that market movements only explain the said percentage of actual returns, but 49.5% is explained by other factors. However, the portfolio of the market is able to significantly influence the change in the actual returns by 0.4.24 units ($p = 0.000$). In addition, the model is significant in explaining the variation in AR, Wald $\chi^2(1) = 32.37$, $p = 0.000$. These findings confirm those by Black, Jensen, and Sholes (1972) who found out that higher beta coefficient and higher expected returns go hand in hand. Furthermore, Fama and MacBeth (1973) also found that beta was positively related with returns for the whole period. In fact, in the current study, all beta coefficients for the five years are positive.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The findings of the regression model showed that the portfolio of the market in 2015 is not fully accounted for by the elements in the five year period CAPM as shown by the intercept t-statistic while the others for 2011 to 2014 are fully supported. Thus, in summary, is that the five year period CAPM is consequently able to predict the outline of portfolio return in Kenya NSE and specifically the listed companies in the agricultural sector. There is also evidence that the magnitude of beta coefficient affects the returns in a given way such that higher betas give higher returns. This implies that the hypothesis stating that CAPM does not predict securities returns in the NSE is rejected and the conclusion is that the actual excess returns on securities in the agricultural sector can be predicted using this model.

Due to the findings and the conclusions arrived at in this study; a number of recommendations are highlighted. There is need to find out the validity of CAPM in the other sectors of the economy to find out if there is consistency with the current study or even other studies done elsewhere. The outcomes of this study support the CAPM's forecast that the intercept should be equal to zero. Nonetheless, there is a strong indication of a positive beta risk as forecast by CAPM. Since the intercept is not different from zero significantly, it renders the findings to be in support of the CAPM.

In utilizing the NSE 20 share index to represent the major stocks for agricultural firms, the findings have tried to provide significant findings that support the CAPM. Thus, for future research, it would be of interest to use other asset pricing models to compare the findings with those found on the CAPM under this study to compare and contrast. In addition, since this study was only centered on historical data from agricultural

sector companies listed on the NSE, it will be of great importance to confirm the findings of this study by carrying out the methodology on non-agricultural sector companies listed on the NSE separately on a sector by sector basis.

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